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FORMING THE STUDENT'S ECOLOGICAL THINKING IN EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES DURING THE TEACHING OF "NATURAL SCIENCE" IN THE 4TH GRADE

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Annotation: In this article, the formation of the student's ecological thinking in the fourth grade of "Natural Science" in extracurricular activities, repetition of knowledge, checking of students' knowledge, learning and skills, extracurricular activities in natural science, their types, the content of extracurricular activities, extracurricular activities conducted with students in the teaching of natural sciences the forms of training are described in detail.

Key words: natural science, ecological thinking, excursion, individual assignments.

Introduction:

Education and upbringing of students at school is carried out in certain forms of educational work. The form of teaching used by the teacher in the process of educational education is organized in accordance with the conditions of conducting educational and cognitive activities of students. The main form of educational work for all subjects studied in schools is the lesson. In the classes, the state curriculum and the educational material specified in the textbook are taught to a certain extent.

Attending classes is mandatory for students. A lesson is a delivery of a certain amount of knowledge from certain subjects to a group of students of a certain age by a specialist with special training. Improving the efficiency of the lesson, raising the level of imparted knowledge, connecting theoretical knowledge with life, teaching with the help of new pedagogical technology, recognizing the knowledge gained by students in natural science, makes students more interested in acquiring knowledge from natural science, helps to strengthen their knowledge.

Literature analysis and methodology:

The entire educational system: a complex of teaching methods, styles and tools is implemented in the lesson. In science classes, students receive theoretical knowledge, practical training and skills under the guidance of the teacher in accordance with the program.

The teacher explains the material clearly to the students, using various educational and visual aids, gives the necessary explanations, teaches the students to work independently with the textbook, and to use their knowledge in practice. The purpose and content of the lessons are different, but the common goal of all of them is the comprehensive education of students and the presentation and consolidation of knowledge that is understandable to them.

The teacher should organize the students' work in such a way that they understand that what is learned in this lesson is related to what was learned before, and that they master the material carefully and understand it.

During the lesson, the teacher should try to create conditions for active work of students, to arouse their interest. This can happen only when preparing for the lesson, using material that is interesting, related to the life of our country, and close to the students.

While preparing for the lesson, it is necessary to take into account not only the content of the new topic, but also the age, development and readiness of the students, the level of assimilation of the previously learned, and the thoroughness of the acquired knowledge. The use of various methods in the lesson makes it possible to fully and clearly cover a new topic, makes students less tired, and increases their activity.

In the course of education, students not only get acquainted with objects and events, but also think about them. This, in turn, leads to the formation of knowledge about the laws of the development of nature in students. The acquisition of educational content of the lesson is characterized not only by the content of the given material, but also by the methods of acquisition of educational materials.

Various forms of educational work are determined in the methodology of teaching natural science. The content of the school course, where the laws of plant, animal and human life and development of nature are studied, determines the uniqueness of the system of teaching this subject at school.

In addition to the main form of natural science teaching - lessons, other forms of educational work conducted by the teacher with students have historically emerged in school practice. In the methodologically correctly organized teaching process, all forms of teaching are interconnected with the main form - the lesson. They develop concepts about nature, worldview, thinking, and practical skills.

In science classes, the teacher uses all teaching methods: oral, visual and practical methods. It shows plants and animals. Students are introduced to the external and internal structure of some organisms by doing practical work. However, the development process of a plant or an animal, which requires long observation, cannot be shown in the lessons, as well as the coexistence of various organisms in natural conditions. That is why special forms are used to supplement lessons in the teaching methodology of natural science.

Excursions introduce plants and animals in natural groupings in nature, agricultural production or museums. The studied materials are included in the set of concepts or strengthen, clarify, deepen, generalize the previously decided concepts.

Excursions are closely connected with the lessons, the objects seen on the excursion are recalled many times during the course, and the collected objects are displayed. In the final field trips, students apply their previously acquired knowledge, make independent observations on assignments and collect material.

It is clear and obvious that the homework of the lessons is especially related to assignments of an experimental nature. Students conduct simple experiments and observations at home. Extracurricular activities are more complicated than homework. Appropriate plants, special tools and other equipment are required for their implementation. Extracurricular activities include: assignments in the living nature corner, educational experience areas, and activities in nature.

Assignments to students for work in science rooms and living nature corner are given in classes for all subjects of the course during the academic year. Various non-compulsory forms of extracurricular activities with students are widely used in the teaching of natural sciences: individual, extracurricular, socially useful work, work of a group of young naturalists, public evenings and other events.

Extracurricular work is organized based on the educational material and depending on it. However, its content does not repeat the lesson. It is not limited to the scope of the program, but complements it and reveals the necessary aspects of natural science.

It is known that in science classes, the teacher uses all teaching methods: oral, visual and practical methods. It shows plants and animals. By performing practical work, students are introduced to the external and internal structure of some organisms.

As we wrote in the previous chapters, it is impossible to show the development process of a plant or an animal, the life of which requires long observation, and the coexistence of various organisms in natural conditions in a classroom lesson. That is why special forms are used to supplement lessons in the teaching methodology of natural science.

On excursions, children are introduced to plants and animals in natural groupings in nature, in agriculture, in museums. Excursions strengthen, clarify, deepen and generalize the previously decided concepts. Excursions are closely connected with lessons: the objects seen on the excursion are remembered many times during the course, and the collected objects are exhibited. In the final excursions, the students consolidate the previously acquired knowledge, conduct independent observations on assignments and collect material.

It is clear and obvious that the lessons are connected with homework, especially with tasks of an experimental nature. Pupils carry out simple experiments and observations at home. This is a special form of teaching based on the highest demonstration and independence of students' creativity.

Results:

Excursions are planned for almost every topic of the program. The natural conditions of our country allow to greatly increase their number. Excursion is one of the most effective forms of teaching, which implies a very complex and difficult form of educational work and various methods of knowledge presentation.

The calendar work plan of the excursion is drawn up at the beginning of the academic year for one quarter, taking into account local conditions. Extracurricular activities are more complicated than homework. For their implementation, appropriate plants, special tools and other equipment are required. Extracurricular work includes: work in the living nature corner, on the training ground, and on summer assignments in nature.

These activities are called extracurricular activities, which are the most common form of extracurricular activities that are carried out under the guidance of the teacher in order to arouse the interest of students in learning, as well as to expand and supplement the school program. Assignments to students for work in science rooms and living nature corner are given in classes for all subjects of the course during the academic year.

Non-compulsory voluntary forms of extracurricular activities with students are widely used in the teaching of natural sciences: individual work, extracurricular work, the work of the "Young Naturalists" circle, public evenings, and socially useful work. Extracurricular work is organized based on the educational material and depending on it. However, its content does not repeat the lesson. It is not limited to the scope of the program, but complements it and reveals interesting and necessary aspects of natural science.

Extracurricular activities in science are one of the means of comprehensive development of the student's personality. Forms of extracurricular activities such as conducting long-term experiments, collecting material for herbariums and collections, preparing models, models and other visual aids, living nature corner and work on the training ground are practical

learning and practical training important for connecting the study of nature with life and for the polytechnic preparation of students. gives you the opportunity to equip yourself with skills.

Practical work on agriculture, which is carried out by children's observations and teacher's explanations, helps them to understand the fundamentals of the doctrine of managing nature and changing it for the benefit of man. Children's social and useful activities teach them to work and help in patriotism education. All types of extracurricular activities should be interdependent and complementary.

Interest in working with plants and animals can be developed in extracurricular activities, especially students interested in natural science can participate in the activities of the young naturalist club. A teacher who notices students' tendency to collect natural objects, love for animals, finds activities based on their interests, and develops the desire to study nature science in depth.

Discussion:

Practical work in nature should be accompanied by observations and reading of relevant books. Individual studies in natural science are conducted with students who have an inclination or at least an interest in learning about nature. The teacher's personality, his love and attitude towards nature, and his ability to follow and interest students play a big role in the development of children's interest in nature.

Not only the quality of students' knowledge, but also their desire to work with science works outside of class depends on how he organizes observations in the 4th grade, how much he justifies the necessity and importance of this work, and how he sets up science teaching.

Completion of individual assignments forms research skills, fills children's free time with useful and interesting activities. The content of individual tasks is determined by the interests of students. No matter what the student is interested in - whether it is caring for indoor plants, collecting stamps or postcards depicting animals and plants, creating a herbarium, conducting experiments and observations in nature - it should be approved and encouraged by the teacher.

Individual tasks are selected depending on the interests of students, but the content of the tasks should organize their implementation and the methodology should be carefully thought out by the teacher. In order to bring the work to the end and not to lose interest in it, it is necessary for the teacher to provide regular assistance to students in the completion of individual assignments.

The main task of the teacher is to provide active work that gives practical results. It is different in work: verbal presentation of teachers and students with the demonstration of natural or pictorial visual aids, social work of students aimed at forming practical learning and skills, and other methods should be properly combined.

Preparation for training is very important for the successful operation of the club. Before the first session, it is necessary to remind about the time of its holding, to introduce students to the tasks of the circle, to think over the content of the introductory interview in all its details. While drawing up the work plan of the circle, it is necessary to discuss the intended topic with the students and take into account their suggestions.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it should be said that one of the forms of extracurricular work in science is group work. It covers a specific range of participants and provides an inherently deeper

learning opportunity. Membership in the circle is voluntary, but the participant undertakes to work according to a clear plan and finish the work he started. The plan should include tasks that students are capable of doing.

Extracurricular activities in science provide an opportunity to expand, deepen and concretize the knowledge gained in lessons, arouse interest in studying nature, develop student activity and independence, and plan time. Science activities outside the classroom have educational value, as these activities have a positive effect on the behavior of students. Their view of the material world and work culture are formed, their interest in learning, independent observation skills develop, and their sense of community and love for nature deepens.

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